

Evaluating computational techniques from image signal processing for finding formulaic language patterns in historical sources

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1 Premise

When a large set of historical documents is used in a research project it is desirable to find formulaic language patterns in an automatic manner. This is however a challenge since the computer has no knowledge of the semantic meaning of the text and it thus raises a number of questions. What method do we use to find the patterns and how do we represent, store and evaluate the quality of a pattern and decide which ones to keep?

Automatically detecting formulaic patterns is challenging for various reasons, but the one that stands out is that patterns contain small variations between the different occurrences of a pattern. There can be small variations in the patterns between two documents due to spelling variation, changes in the use of the pattern over time or change of grammar of the language over time. Patterns can occur anywhere in the text, meaning they don't have to start in the same exact position in each document. Two patterns do not have to occur in the same order in two documents. It is desirable that no human input is required in determining the patterns. The goal of the algorithm is to find the structure of the documents so that it is easier to explore the material. Human input would introduce a potential bias and would require prior knowledge of the material.

This paper proposes to use methods from image and audio signal processing to evaluate whether the approach behind them can be helpful in the domain of computational historical research. More specifically image compression, noise reduction and image classification. At first glance it might not be obvious how these techniques are related to the problem of formulaic language. The image techniques listed have in common that they try to represent the essentials of the image in a more compact form. They keep the structure of the image and diminish the variation. Formulaic language patterns lend structure to a text and function as anchor points in the text. In that sense they fulfill a similar role.

Within the domain of signal processing and machine learning for images there are numerous techniques that look for patterns that are not repeated in the exact same way. The premise of this paper is that there is value in considering whether such techniques can help solve the formulaic patterns finding challenge.

There are three techniques that are relevant for this premise; image compression, image classification and image denoising. Image compression means trading image quality for a reduction in memory usage and storage space. Image classification is a way for a computer to distinguish images and automatically put them in one predefined category. Image denoising is a method to remove unintentional image defects such as spots on photos and reconstruct missing areas.

When looking at the results of image compression the fact that under low memory budgets the basic structure of a picture is still visible stands out. A similar observation can be made for image classification. Image classification is done on the basis of the structure of the images, details are not taken into consideration. In the image approaches the structure is determined by forcing the data into a lower dimensional representation than the original. Could a similar approach on textual content in the same way reveal the structure of the text?

To evaluate the quality of a set of language patterns we need a way to differentiate one set of patterns from another. For images it is relatively easy to assess the quality of the representation in a computational way by

calculating the difference in brightness and color between a compressed representation and the original. For text this is more difficult. A missing word or a changed word can cause a large difference in the meaning of the text but only constitute a small numerical difference in the representation. We propose to differentiate by counting how many words a collection of patterns can correctly reconstruct from the original text.

We first identify the various image processing techniques that are relevant to find patterns in signal based on sparse encoding. We then discuss how these techniques can be modified to work on textual content. Lastly we assess which of the approaches is the most likely to be successful in the search for patterns.

2 Image compression and single value decomposition (SVD)

Image compression is a way to store the an image in less memory and storage space on disc. It accomplishes this by finding and keeping the essential parts of the image, while discarding the outliers. Images are represented in a matrix of height and width. On each position an integer value is stored. In the case of a black and white image the integer values range from 0 to 255, where zero represents black and 255 presents white, and the values in between represent different shades of gray going from darker to lighter. In color images three values will be stored per position of the matrix, representing red, green blue respectively.

The compression is accomplished by decomposing the original matrix in a sequence of single rank matrices that approximate the original matrix. The algorithm is called Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) which finds it's origin in linear algebra. A 1 rank matrix consists of a single row and column. We can approximate the matrix by a one row matrix and one column matrix and multiplying them with each other.

SVD is a way to find out what is the best approximation for a matrix in a low dimension. It is a form of dimension reduction.

SVD returns three matrices S , U and V . The first matrix contains all the columns of the 1 rank approximation. Going over the ranks in the SVD matrices step by step reconstructs the matrix.

What would be the equivalent of SVD on text? There are a number of differences here between text and images. An image is two dimensional. A text is a single dimension. so we need multiple, or divide single text into parts. Deerwester et al introduce Latent Semantic Analysis (LSA).¹ LSA applies SVD on multiple documents with this Document-term vectorization per document we can apply it to a set of texts. This however does not provide the patterns. Because document-term vectorization doesn't store the full order of the terms, just returning the SVD matrices is not enough.

SVD is used to calculate a semantic distance between documents, i.e. given a document it can query for and return similar documents. That is not the same aim as we have at this workshop.

3 Image denoising and reconstruction using k-SVD

In Aharon et al the authors introduce an algorithm called k-SVD.² k-SVD is a form of dictionary learning. Given a vector it tries to reconstruct it as best as possible from atoms in a dictionary. The idea behind all these compression and feature dimension reduction methods is to use a base vector so that the distance between the base vector and a specific vector is as small as possible. When we work with multiple vectors for multiple documents a single base vector complimented by the next ranks in the matrix approaches gives a better on better approximation of the original matrix, but it doesn't provide us with the patterns that we are looking for.

1. Scott Deerwester et al., "Indexing by latent semantic analysis," *Journal of the American Society for Information Science* 41, no. 6 (1990): 391–407, <http://www3.interscience.wiley.com/cgi-bin/abstract/10049585/ABSTRACT>.

2. M. Aharon, M. Elad, and A. Bruckstein, "K-SVD: An algorithm for designing overcomplete dictionaries for sparse representation," *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing* 54, no. 11 (2006): 4311–4322, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TSP.2006.881199>.

In the vector there are as many dimensions as there are features, i.e. as many as there are bi skipgrams in the vocabulary. Some documents agree with each other in some dimensions in certain vectors and in some other dimensions in others.

K-SVD is a variant of k-means which is used for clustering purposes. The original vector is compared to a cluster of atoms. SVD is used to calculate the smallest difference with the existing atoms.

In Bryt and Elad the authors use k-SVD to compress a collection of images of faces.³

In Lebrun and Leclaire they train an algorithm based on a set of training images with the aim of removing the noise in the images.⁴

Jun Fu et al use k-SVD to compress a set of images.⁵

4 Image classification and denoising through convolutional neural network (CNN)

Image classification is done with an encoder based on a convolutional neural network (CNN), Image classification is a semi automated task where the neural network returns a value for each of the predetermined categories. A convolutional filter works by taking an area of the image and performing a calculation over which results in a smaller area. A convolutional network has multiple filters. Every filter does a different transformation, meaning that different filters react to different kinds of images. .

3. Ori Bryt and Michael Elad, "Compression of facial images using the K-SVD algorithm," *Journal of Visual Communication and Image Representation* 19, no. 4 (2008): 270–282, ISSN: 1047-3203, <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvcir.2008.03.001>, <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1047320308000254>.

4. Marc Lebrun and Arthur Leclaire, "An Implementation and Detailed Analysis of the K-SVD Image Denoising Algorithm," <https://doi.org/10.5201/ipol.2012.llm-ksvd>, *Image Processing On Line* 2 (2012): 96–133.

5. Jun Fu et al., "Clustering K-SVD for sparse representation of images," *EURASIP Journal on Advances in Signal Processing* 2019, no. 1 (October 2019): 47, ISSN: 1687-6180, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13634-019-0650-4>, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13634-019-0650-4>.

In Haque et al the authors implement Image denoising using a neural network works with a CNN as a encoder, but instead of stopping after the hidden layer, that returns a single number mapping to a category. A denoising neural network has a decoder that does the opposite action of the convolution.⁶ There are two ways to do that: a deconvolution filter or a RNN network.

A convolutional neural network encoder and decoder is used in image denoising, alternative is a convolutional neural network encoder and a LSTM decoder. This works better with restoring deleted, lost parts of images. The convolutional encoder goes from 4x4 to 3x3 to 2x2 to 1x1. It takes two adjacent values, weights them according to the weights of the filter and generates a single value. A deconvolutional filter works the other way around: it generates a 2x2 from a 1x1 image/matrix, a 3x3 image from a 2x2 image/matrix etc. The filters can be applied on submatrices side by side, or by a sliding window with overlapping submatrices.

This approach is interesting because the trained filters in an image classification task show clearly the different categories that are being trained, i.e. faces of persons, or different animals. The filters seem to capture a generic impression of the characteristics of each of the categories that we want to recognize.

A convolutional neural network filter can also be applied on textual content. In Bengio et al the authors use a convolutional filter to build a language model where the model can return short phrases three or five words long that frequently occur within the same context.⁷

Each word of the input is assigned it's own word vector. Words that have the same semantic meaning occur close to each other in the vector space. In the work mentioned above the word embedding space is determined at the same time as the training of the filters. The words embedding can also

6. Kazi Nazmul Haque, Mohammad Abu Yousuf, and Rajib Rana, *Image denoising and restoration with CNN-LSTM Encoder Decoder with Direct Attention*, 2018, arXiv: 1801.05141 [stat.ML].

7. Yoshua Bengio, Réjean Ducharme, and Pascal Vincent, "A Neural Probabilistic Language Model," in *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, ed. T. Leen, T. Dietterich, and V. Tresp, vol. 13 (MIT Press, 2000), https://proceedings.neurips.cc/paper_files/paper/2000/file/728f206c2a01bf572b5940d7d9a8fa4c-Paper.pdf.

be trained ahead of the training of the convolution filters by using Word2Vec or Fast text.⁸

In Pham et al the authors discuss the use of CNN for language models.⁹

5 Evaluation and outlook

Now we discuss which of the methods are the most suitable for pattern detection. We mentioned SVD, k-SVD and CNN in the previous sections. All methods use a sparse representation as the basis of the solution.

Which method is the best match with the question of finding the formulaic patterns in historic documents? SVD works well on a single image, but the concept is not easy to convert to a single text. A single document represents a single dimension. SVD works by finding the repeated patterns on the horizontal as well as the vertical axis within an image. The single versus multiple dimensions problem can be tackled by applying SVD on multiple documents at the same time or by splitting a single document into multiple fragments. Apart from the the difference in the number of dimensions, textual content has another difference. It is not expressed in gradients. LSA solves this problem by vectorizing the text as a document-term matrix. This however loses all the position information. LSA finds a semantic distance between documents. That is not suitable for our goal of finding formulaic patterns.

K-SVD finds the combination of atoms that result in the closest representation of the input image. Then the original inputs are reconstructed from the atoms. The atoms are updated based on how far the recreation of the original images is from the sparse representation.

8. Tomas Mikolov et al., "Distributed Representations of Words and Phrases and their Compositionality," in *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, ed. C.J. Burges et al., vol. 26 (Curran Associates, Inc., 2013), https://proceedings.neurips.cc/paper_files/paper/2013/file/9aa42b31882ec039965f3c4923ce901b-Paper.pdf.

9. Ngoc-Quan Pham, German Kruszewski, and Gemma Boleda, "Convolutional Neural Network Language Models," in *Proceedings of the 2016 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing*, ed. Jian Su, Kevin Duh, and Xavier Carreras (Austin, Texas: Association for Computational Linguistics, November 2016), 1153–1162, <https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/D16-1123>, <https://aclanthology.org/D16-1123>.

The general workflow is that there is a set of documents is tokenized, normalized and turned into vectors. Then we apply different approaches as encoders to the vectors to find the patterns. The patterns are the hidden layer. After that follows a decoder. It takes the data from the hidden layer and reproduces the vectors. The hidden layer can only contain a limit set of patterns. The decoder takes the patterns and tries to reconstruct the original as best as possible. The quality of the patterns can then be measured by taking the difference between the original vectors and the reconstructed ones.

To make textual content work with machine learning we need to convert the words into numbers, ie. vectors. How to vectorize this in text? One way we can encode the textual content as a vector is by replacing every token with a number. We create a vocabulary by going over all the tokens in the documents and finding all the unique words, sorting them alphabetically and assigning them a number. A challenge is that a vocabulary does not give a range. Another challenge with this approach is that small additions or deletions would shift the starting positions of patterns between documents and make the detection of patterns more difficult.

For the vectorization it is important that we can distinguish the different features of a document. The exact position of a word in a document is not important, only the relative position, meaning only the surrounding words, preceding and succeeding are of importance. A well known alternative is to encode it as a term frequency vector. We discard the position information, and encode text of a document as a vector of sorted terms of documents and encoding the number of occurrences of a term per position. This has the advantage that each column now has the same feature on it independent of the document. We also have ranges per feature now, that being the frequency, which we can scale. We now have two new challenges: the frequency per term differs quite a bit and second we don't have position information anymore which means that we don't know how to reconstruct a pattern from the matrix, especially since many terms are repeated.

Bigram encoding we take each pair of subsequent tokens as a single vocabulary word. Bigram encoding reduces the amount of occurrence per

term strongly. However, most of the terms become unique. This has advantages in the sense that the witnesses can be reconstructed, since every term can be uniquely located within a witness. However finding formulaic patterns relies on the fact that terms are repeated and in combinations form patterns. Small variations in patterns will not be found by using traditional bigrams.

Skip bigrams is a variant technique on skipgrams. Instead of two adjacent tokens skipgrams can take any combination of terms that occurs in the document with a space with a one or two tokens that are not part of the gram. This approach combines the advantages of the previous encodings.

The combination of the skip bigram vectorization and k-SVD approach seem to have the most potential.

6 Conclusion

The standard SVD works on a single image, its text equivalent Latent Semantic Indexing works on a set of documents, but only returns a semantic distance measure and not a pattern. Standard SVD and LSA are disqualified on those grounds. Convolution filters require a large amount of training. Not only the convolution filters themselves have to be trained but also their counterpart, either a deconvolutional filter or a LSTM. Outside of the training process the deconvolution filter of LSTM that we use for decoding the witnesses is of no value. This leaves k-SVD based dictionary learning as the method with the most potential compared to the other approaches. Combined with a skip bigram vectorization which is able to deal with small variations within patterns.

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